

Parents' Attitude towards Secondary School Students' Moral Behaviour

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Abstract

The study investigated the influence of parent's attitude on the immoral behaviour of secondary school students in Ado Ekiti Local Government. It also examined the influence of the student immoral behaviour on the moral behaviour of the students on their educational progress. The study employed descriptive of the survey type. The population was all the secondary school students in Ado Ekiti Local Government. The sample consisted of 120 secondary school students randomly selected from 12 secondary schools drawn from Ado-Ekiti Local Government of Ekiti State. The method of selection was by multistage sampling procedure. The instrument employed for the study was a questionnaire titled: "The Moral Behaviour of Secondary School Students Questionnaire (SCQ)", consisting of five sections. The validity and the reliability of the instrument was ensured. The instrument was administered by the researcher with the assistance of research assistants. Descriptive and inferential statistics were used to analyze the data collected. All hypotheses were tested at 0.05 level of significance. The findings of the study revealed that parents' attitudes significantly influenced the moral behaviour of students. It was also revealed that the moral behaviour of students influenced their educational progress. It was recommended among others that moral behaviour should form part of the criteria for evaluating the educational progress of students.

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Introduction

Moral could be described as the principle or standard of right and wrong in behaviour, and the differences between good and evil. It is crystal clear that education which has to do with acquisition of knowledge develops the learners both intellectually and morally. If the development is limited to intellectual aspect, education is not complete. Drifte (2016) argued that the possession of knowledge without positive attitudes, values and moral development of human beings is as good as a wooden idol. In the society today, particularly among secondary school students, immoral behaviours such as truancy, lateness, cultism, drug abuse, disrespect of elders, sexual harassment, rape, stealing, rioting, armed robbery, unwanted pregnancy, abortion, laziness, homosexuality, lesbianism, examination misconduct and other social vices seems to be on the increase. prevalent and it appears to be in fluency the students educational progress negatively.

Moral behaviour according to Drifte (2016) moral behaviour is referred to as the laid down laws and standard guiding people's behaviour of people in the society. Although it varies from place to place because behaviours that are culturally considered unethical in one society could be acceptable in another which denotes that there is no universal standard of determining behaviour. Immoral behaviour is defined differently by various scholars, according to Gross (2018) immoral behaviours are such that do harm to the environment and people's life, society, civilisation and so on. Based on his understanding of immoral behaviour, he believed that it could lead people away from activities that are beneficiary to them. In the perspective of Chauhan (2020), immoral behaviour is any behaviour which is contrary to the norms and culture of the society of which one is committed in and this could be influenced by factors such as parent's attitude and so on. Immoral behaviour according to Dash (2019) is defined as none conforming to the patterns of conduct usually accepted or established as consistent with principles of personal and social ethics. As observed by the researcher, someone may conclude that these kinds of behaviours could be totally unacceptable because they are deemed wrong and harmful if based on moral and societal norms.

In the past, it seems there was a good balance of both intellectual and moral standards among students in schools when parents are committed to the general welfare of their children. Then, it appears to be high degree of morality in schools when parents and teachers shared the same view of students' desirable and undesirable behaviour demonstrated by the student unlike nowadays, one could notice several manifestations of immorality in students' life that could be enhanced by different factors.

As observed, parent attitude could be a factor, as parents are too busy to perform their expected roles in child upbringing. More so, any child that is not properly monitored and disciplined by the parent could exhibit any kind of behaviour either morally acceptable or not. Based on the freedom, such students are likely to be dominated by self-will and shun anything that may want to impede their freedom that could be very dangerous to them because adolescence stage is full of many irrationalities and anti-social behaviour, like disobedience, laziness, violation of rules, sexual pervasion and so on if not monitored could be harmful to the fulfilment of their career in life (Cardwell & Flanagan, 2018).

If examined vividly, immoral behaviours could have destructive effects on the educational progress of students. For instance, untamed child may find it difficult to conform to the school rules and regulations. A student that is not regular in school, always late, involving in drug abuse, cultism, sexual pervasion and so on are likely to perform poorly in his studies and thereby affects his educational progress (Gross, 2018).

The importance of moral aspect of education is pertinent for a fruitful success in educational pursuit, this was recognized by policy makers in education, and the importance was clearly spelled out in the National Policy on Education (Agulanna & Onukaogu, 2012). In spite of the efforts of teachers on students' moral acts, lots of immoral behaviours immoral behaviours are prevalent among secondary school students such as truancy, lateness, cultism, drug abuse, disobedience, sexual violence, indecent dressing, rioting, armed robbery, unwanted pregnancy, abortion, laziness, homosexuality, lesbianism, examination malpractice and so on. No solution and they are taking more roots among our secondary school students. Due to the persistent of immoral behaviours among secondary school students, a lot of students, who would have made the nation proud, have lost their lives through violence. Some have dropped out of school as a result pregnancy. There are some who have become nuisance to the society as a result of their inability to complete their secondary school education, based on this background, there is need to investigate the factors responsible for the immoral behaviours of secondary school students in Ado Local Government and probable ways of extirpating the problems.

The purpose of this study was to investigate the influence of parent's attitude on the immoral behaviour of secondary school students in Ado Ekiti Local Government. It also examined the influence of the student immoral behaviour on the moral behaviour of the students on their educational progress.

Research Hypotheses

1. Parents' attitudes will not significantly influence the moral behaviours of students.
2. The moral behaviour of students will not significantly influence the educational progress.

Methodology

The study employed descriptive of the survey type, and it was considered appropriate because it focused on existing characteristics of a particular group to satisfy the need for better understanding of the moral behaviour of secondary school students. The population was all the secondary school students in Ado Ekiti Local Government. The sample consisted of 120 secondary school students randomly selected from 12 secondary schools drawn from Ado-Ekiti Local Government of Ekiti State. The method of selection was by multistage sampling procedure. The instrument employed for the study was a questionnaire titled: "The Moral Behaviour of Secondary School Students Questionnaire (SCQ)", consisting of five sections. The validity and the reliability of the instrument was ensured. The instrument was administered by the researcher with the assistance of research assistants. Descriptive statistics and inferential statistics were used to analyze the data collected. t-test was used to test the two hypotheses generated at 0.05 level of significance.

Hypothesis Testing

Hypothesis 1: Parents' attitudes will not significantly influence the moral behaviours of students.

Table 1: t-test showing the influence of parents' attitudes on the moral behaviour of students.

Variable	N	Mean	SD	df	t-cal	t-table
Parents' attitude	120	12.08	1.081	119	213.519	1.980
Moral behaviour	120	61.83	3.18			

P < 0.05

Table 1 shows that t-cal (213.519) is greater than t-table (1.980) at 0.05 level of significance. The null hypothesis is rejected. This implies that parents' attitudes will significantly influence the moral behaviour of students.

Hypothesis 2: The moral behaviour of students will not significantly influence the educational progress.

Table 2: t-test showing the influence of moral behaviour of students on their educational progress.

Variable	N	Mean	SD	df	t-cal	t-table
Moral behaviour	120	61.83	3.18	119	216.633	1.980
Educational progress	120	8.63	1.16			

$P < 0.05$

Table 2 shows that t-cal (216.633) is greater than t-table (1.980) at 0.05 level of significance. The null hypothesis is rejected. This implies that the moral behaviour of students will significantly influence their educational progress.

Discussion

The study also showed that parents' attitudes significantly influenced the moral behaviour of students. This finding is supported by Fagan (1995), who argued that the immoral behaviours of adolescents are traceable to their family background. He opined that there are seven family conditions that can lead to immoral behaviour of adolescents and these include: fatherless families; the absence of mother's love; parental fighting and domestic violence; lack of parental supervision and discipline; rejection of the child; parental abuse or neglect; and criminal parents. Hart and Carlo (2005) also posited that the home environment is important in developing the personality of child. There is a face-to-face contact between the parents and children, which determine the personality and character of child, and developing upon the status of parent's active relations and other social set up of home. This position of Umme Kulsum is supported by the finding of this research. The study of Kennedy (2010) showed that the home environment affects the students' moral values. Many people are raising children and looking to others for answers, whether it is day care centers, schools, evangelists, counsellors, or the government. The finding of this research has confirmed the truth of this claim.

The study also showed that the moral behaviour of students significantly influenced their educational progress. The findings agree with Hart and Carlo (2005) that if self-respect prevails in the school situation, learners will learn self-discipline. If there is self-discipline, there are more chances of having direction in the fulfilment of the learners' goal, so positive academic achievement is possible. Dash (2019) also posited that if discipline [effective] is present at school and the parent at home is also aware of good discipline at school and it is also applied at home, this is a good recipe for good academic achievement because what is applied at school is also applied at home. Drifte (2016) also opined that if there is no proper family environment social differences and learners are from disadvantaged social areas, this could lead to bad discipline and negative results academically.

Conclusion

Based on the findings of this study, it was concluded that parents' attitudes significantly influenced the moral behaviour of students. It was also concluded that the moral behaviour of students influenced their educational progress.

Recommendations

Based on the findings, the following recommendations were made:

1. Moral behaviour should form part of the criteria for evaluating the educational progress of students.
2. There should be good relationship between the school and the home, because the moral development of the students is beyond what the school can handle. Hence, establishment of Parents Teachers Association (PTA) is expedient.
3. The school should be organized in such a way that guarantors to ascertain good moral behaviour students.
4. Parents should show more interest and concern on the education of their children to complement the efforts of the school.
5. Students should abide with the school rules and regulations to enhance good moral that will influence excellent academic performance and educational progress.

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